

Exploring the association between AI tool use and academic self-efficacy among university students in Israel

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ABSTRACT

Academic self-efficacy, understood as students' belief in their capability to manage academic tasks and overcome challenges, is widely recognized as a key factor in educational success. In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) tools, such as adaptive learning systems, virtual tutors, and AI-driven analytics, have been increasingly integrated into higher education. This correlational study examines the association between students' engagement with AI tools and their perceived academic self-efficacy in Israeli universities. Based on self-report data from 102 undergraduate and graduate students, collected through a validated academic self-efficacy questionnaire, the study examines how the frequency and nature of AI tool usage relate to students' confidence in handling academic challenges. The results reveal a weak but statistically significant positive correlation between AI usage and self-efficacy. As this is a correlational study, no causal conclusions can be drawn. Nonetheless, the findings may provide preliminary insights for curriculum developers and educational policymakers aiming to support student motivation through the informed use of AI technologies. Further research is needed to explore the specific types of AI tools that may support academic confidence and how their long-term use interacts with students' self-directed learning. These findings underscore the relevance of AI integration in higher education and highlight the need for thoughtful implementation strategies that enhance students' academic confidence and learning autonomy.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, higher education, universities, students, self-efficacy, learning.

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INTRODUCTION

The present study investigates the relationship between two key variables: students' use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools and their academic self-efficacy. Although AI tools are increasingly being integrated into higher education, there is limited empirical evidence on how these tools affect students' confidence in their academic abilities. Academic self-efficacy, defined as students' belief in their capability to complete academic tasks successfully, plays a critical role in learning outcomes.

While AI tools are now widely used by students for

academic purposes, their actual impact on academic self-efficacy is still not fully understood. Most existing studies examine AI adoption in technical terms or focus on educators' perspectives (Zhai et al., 2021; Lampropoulos and Kinshuk, 2024), leaving open questions about how students themselves perceive and use these tools. Furthermore, prior research has often addressed AI or self-efficacy as isolated topics rather than examining their interrelation (Baherimoghadam et al., 2021; Li et al., 2023; Holmes et al., 2019).

The current study addresses this gap by focusing specifically on higher-education students and investigating the correlation between their use of AI tools and their academic self-efficacy. This focus is particularly timely, as it captures a unique moment in the educational landscape – the first full academic year (2023–2024) following the mass availability of generative AI tools such as ChatGPT. At that time, most institutions had not yet established clear guidelines or frameworks for AI use in education, allowing this research to reflect authentic and unstructured adoption patterns among students.

Understanding how AI tools influence students' academic self-efficacy can help institutions design better learning environments, develop student-centered AI policies, and support learners more effectively. Additionally, these insights provide a valuable foundation for future longitudinal or cross-cultural research into technology-enhanced learning and student psychology.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In today's digital age, artificial intelligence (AI) is quickly developing and affecting many areas, one of which is education. In education, a wide variety of tools and technologies exist that are intended to improve and personalize the learning and teaching process. These technologies include adaptive learning systems, virtual teachers, learning analytics tools, and more. Higher education marks a transition from teacher-led learning to more independent learning, and students are required to develop autonomous learning strategies and acquire high self-efficacy to succeed at their studies and, later, at their careers. AI tools may be very useful for this purpose; therefore, it is important to investigate how effective these tools are in helping higher-education students acquire self-efficacy and reach high academic achievements. The current study examines how the use of AI technologies influences self-efficacy among higher-education students, a topic that is gaining interest in the research of education and learning psychology (Luckin et al., 2016).

Recent reviews emphasize the importance of mapping the conceptual structure of AI in education and highlight emerging applications such as intelligent tutoring, predictive analytics, and generative AI, pointing to significant gaps in theory-driven research (Wang et al., 2024).

Self-efficacy, a term which was first introduced by Bandura (Bandura, 1997; N. Li et al., 2023), is defined as a person's belief in their ability to organize and perform the required actions to reach specific goals (Baherimoghadam et al., 2021). According to Bandura, if an individual believes that they can complete a specific action in the learning process, their level of self-efficacy and their aspiration to perform that action will be high (Li et al., 2023), since it seems to drive the individual's motivation

and to lead their learning process (Baherimoghadam et al., 2021).

The study shows that the use of AI tools increases self-efficacy; however, students do not tend to use AI tools for their studies more than non-students use these tools, maybe due to psychological reasons (Chan, 2023; Davidovitch and Wadmany, 2021; Keleş and Aydın, 2021). Nonetheless, students were found to have higher self-efficacy than non-students. The study suggests that, although students already possess high self-efficacy, AI tools are helpful in further increasing student self-efficacy, especially in more demanding courses, as well as strengthening the self-efficacy of less confident students. In addition, the use of AI tools in learning may save time, help to make personalized learning materials more accessible, and improve the learning process by providing students with immediate feedback, interactive learning, and new tools for assimilating the learning material. The use of AI tools also leads to higher academic achievements and prevents burnout (Harry and Sayudin, 2023; Holmes et al., 2019; Luckin et al., 2016).

AI-based tools offer several significant advantages in the educational context. They assist teachers in classroom management and in understanding the individual needs of students. They analyze educational data and generate insights that help teachers improve their teaching methods and adapt their methods to the changing needs of students. These tools also reduce the workload on teachers, enabling them to focus on the more creative and interactive aspects of teaching (Bendriem et al., 2018). Also, education based on such technology may not only strengthen learning outcomes but also expand the boundaries of students' knowledge and areas of interest (Tzivion, 2021).

Practical applications of artificial intelligence in education

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has revolutionised modern education by enhancing the learning experience, personalizing instruction, and automating administrative tasks. AI applications in education can be broadly categorized into several areas that support both students and educators. Below is an overview of the main AI-driven tools and their impact on the learning process.

Adaptive learning and personalized education

AI-driven adaptive learning systems adjust educational content in real time to match the learning pace and preferences of individual students. One prominent example is Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS), which uses artificial intelligence to provide students with immediate, personalized feedback and guidance. Platforms such as

Carnegie Learning and Squirrel AI have demonstrated the potential of ITS to improve student engagement and learning outcomes (Chen et al., 2020; Li et al., 2024). Additionally, AI is employed in customized learning paths, with platforms like Coursera, Duolingo, and Khan Academy using user data to suggest courses and exercises based on learners' progress. This allows for greater personalization and supports self-directed learning (Luckin et al., 2016). Another application includes early intervention systems, which identify students struggling with specific concepts and deliver timely support and resources to prevent academic failure (García-Martínez et al., 2023). These adaptive technologies enhance student engagement by offering tailored educational experiences and ensuring that no learner is left behind.

Automated assessment and feedback

Artificial intelligence reduces the workload of educators by automating grading processes and providing timely, personalized feedback. Automated essay grading tools, such as Grammarly and Turnitin, assess writing quality, grammar, and structure, thereby enhancing students' writing skills and enabling instructors to allocate more time for direct teaching (Chen et al., 2020). Formative assessment platforms like Gradescope use AI to evaluate student assignments and provide immediate feedback, which supports students' self-regulated learning and reduces turnaround time for grading (Luckin et al., 2016). Additionally, speech recognition technologies are used in language learning applications such as SpeechAce and Rosetta Stone. These tools use AI-based feedback to help students improve their pronunciation and fluency, contributing to more effective language acquisition (Clark and Mayer, 2016). By streamlining grading and assessment tasks, AI allows educators to focus more on instruction and student support, ultimately improving the overall quality of education (Chen et al., 2020; García-Martínez et al., 2023).

AI-powered virtual assistants and chatbots

AI-powered virtual assistants and chatbots enhance student interaction and provide academic support outside the classroom environment. Tools such as IBM Watson and ChatGPT are widely used to answer student questions, assist with research, and offer personalized explanations (Ravšelj et al., 2025). One notable example is Georgia Tech's "Jill Watson," an AI-based academic advisor that helps students navigate course selections and administrative procedures, offering timely responses to routine academic inquiries (Ed (chatbot), 2024). These AI-driven systems offer 24/7 learning support, increasing accessibility for students who study during non-traditional

hours or in asynchronous learning environments (Chen et al., 2020; Luckin et al., 2016). By ensuring continuous academic guidance and immediate feedback, AI-powered assistants can help maintain student engagement and reduce academic frustration.

AI in educational content creation

Artificial intelligence is increasingly used to generate and improve instructional materials for educators. Tools such as ScribeSense can assist in creating AI-generated lesson plans aligned with curriculum standards, while summarization platforms like QuillBot help condense complex texts for easier comprehension. AI-powered video tools such as Synthesia also support remote learning by producing engaging multimedia content. These technologies reduce teachers' administrative burden and enable them to focus more on student-centered instructional strategies (Chen et al., 2020).

AI in classroom management and administrative tasks

Artificial intelligence supports educators by streamlining classroom management and automating administrative responsibilities. Smart attendance systems using facial recognition technology, such as Face++, can automatically record student attendance with minimal manual input. AI-based scheduling software optimizes class timetables and allocates resources efficiently, easing logistical challenges. According to García-Martínez et al. (2023), learning analytics tools play a key role in identifying at-risk students by analyzing academic data and suggesting timely, targeted interventions. These applications reduce administrative workloads, enabling teachers to focus more on high-quality instruction and student engagement.

AI for special education and inclusive learning

AI-driven technologies provide tailored support for students with diverse learning needs, enhancing accessibility and inclusion across educational contexts. Programs like Google's Project Euphonia assist students with speech disorders, while tools such as Read&Write and Otter.ai offer text-to-speech and speech-to-text functionalities for those with dyslexia or visual impairments. Additionally, real-time AI translation technologies help non-native speakers engage with course materials in their preferred language. As Fitas (2024) and Yap et al. (2025) show, such inclusive AI solutions effectively address communication barriers and learning challenges, enabling equitable participation in education for all learners.

AI in research and academic writing

AI tools play a growing role in supporting research and academic writing by facilitating literature discovery, content generation, and integrity assurance. Platforms like Semantic Scholar and Elicit.ai assist researchers in identifying relevant academic sources, while AI-based writing assistants such as ChatGPT and Jasper offer summarization and style suggestions. Additionally, plagiarism detection software like Turnitin helps uphold academic standards by identifying duplicate content. By enhancing research efficiency, AI not only accelerates academic progress but also encourages higher-order thinking and critical engagement with scholarly material (Zhai et al., 2021).

AI in gamified and immersive learning

AI-powered gamification and immersive technologies enhance student engagement by creating interactive and motivational learning environments. According to a recent systematic review, combining virtual reality (VR) and game elements significantly increases student motivation, immersion, and personalized learning opportunities compared to standard classroom methods. Platforms such as Kahoot! and Quizlet foster real-time interaction and competitiveness, while VR/AR tools like Microsoft HoloLens enable learners to experience complex subjects through immersive simulations (Lampropoulos and Kinshuk, 2024). By supporting active participation and experiential learning, these technologies make the educational process more engaging and effective. Li et al. (2024), who examined the use of digital learning games, found that such tools help students develop higher self-efficacy. Participants in the study reported that they were able to tackle academic challenges in an enjoyable and stimulating way, which increased their motivation to learn and contributed to better academic performance. The games also provided a safe, non-threatening environment that strengthened students' belief in their ability to succeed.

The integration of artificial intelligence in education offers vast potential to personalize learning, automate administrative tasks, and improve student engagement. From adaptive learning and automated assessment to immersive virtual environments, AI is transforming traditional education methods. As AI technology continues to advance, its role in enhancing student success and educational efficiency may become increasingly significant.

AI integration in education

The term "artificial intelligence" was coined in 1955 by

John McCarthy, who defined it as "causing a machine to behave in ways that would be considered intelligent if performed by a human" (Cope et al., 2021). AI technology is based on the process of creating human thinking patterns and building machines that can mimic humans. These machines can solve problems, create plans, and perform a variety of other tasks that would normally require human intelligence (Fitria, 2021; Oran, 2023). This is possible because AI technology works "from bottom to top" and implements existing methods to assess how students learn, while trying to imitate the way that the human mind works (Tzivion, 2021).

Education in the 21st century requires literacy that is suited to the modern times, including a range of skills such as digital literacy, higher-order thinking skills, collaborative abilities, communication and language skills, and ethical conduct in the information age when using online media (Forkosh-Baruch, 2021). In recent years, AI has infiltrated the educational world and has become significantly valuable in education due to the learning experience and efficiency that it offers (Zhai et al., 2021).

Despite the many advantages, the use of AI in education also presents challenges. One of the primary issues is safeguarding the privacy and security of student information. The extensive data repositories necessary for AI systems to function efficiently raise concerns about the handling of sensitive personal data. Additionally, there are worries about over-reliance on technology and a decline in personal interaction between teachers and students (Selwyn, 2019). Furthermore, AI is also viewed as a threatening phenomenon in certain sectors of society, due to its broad potential to replace many professions worldwide (Oran, 2023). A growing body of research indicates that students find ChatGPT especially useful for brainstorming ideas, summarising academic texts, and boosting their productivity, while also voicing concerns about academic integrity and ethical use (Ravšelj et al., 2025).

AI has the potential to transform both society and education, as it is often seen as a solution to various issues such as teacher shortages, student performance, and achievement gaps between students (Oran, 2023). However, a study by Davidovitch and Wadmany, which explores the attitudes of lecturers and students towards the advantages and disadvantages of online teaching during the coronavirus pandemic, indicates that neither students nor lecturers strongly favour online learning (Davidovitch and Wadmany, 2021). Similarly, Keles and Aydin (2021), who investigated students' attitudes towards AI, discovered that most participants held more negative than positive views. One reason for these negative perceptions may be found in a study by Chan, which examines attitudes towards and the implications of using AI technology in education. For instance, ChatGPT is a chatbot capable of handling various text-based requests, including answering simple questions, responding to

complex inquiries such as crafting detailed passages, and assisting individuals in challenging situations (Oran, 2023). The study revealed that both students and teachers share concerns about the misuse of AI tools, such as using ChatGPT for assignments. Furthermore, both groups reported having limited experience in using AI technologies (Chan, 2023).

Despite these findings, a review article by Chen et al. (2020) found that AI helps teachers achieve higher quality in their teaching activities and improves the overall learning experience and learning quality. Furthermore, a meta-analysis found that AI has positive effects on student performance, and, in addition, an increase was found in student attitudes toward learning and student motivation levels (García-Martínez et al., 2023). Regarding student achievements, a study that examines the impact of ChatGPT in education, specifically among undergraduate computer-science students, shows that using ChatGPT significantly increases student self-efficacy (Yilmaz and Karaoglan Yilmaz, 2023). Additionally, a study by Bendriem et al. (2018), which focuses on using learning analytics to improve student outcomes, shows that the use of learning analytics contributes to significant improvements in student achievements and to a decrease in dropout rates.

Self-efficacy

The term “self-efficacy” was first defined by Bandura (as cited in Harari et al., 2023) as the extent to which an individual believes in their ability to organize and successfully perform a series of behaviors that are required to achieve a specific goal. According to Bandura, if an individual believes that they **can** complete a specific action in the learning process, their level of self-efficacy and their aspiration to perform that action will be high (Li et al., 2023), since it seems to drive the individual’s motivation and to lead their learning process (Baherimoghadam et al., 2021). Bandura’s social learning theory (Bandura, 1997) suggests that previous experiences of success and failure, social influences, and cognitive processes shape an individual’s sense of efficacy. In other words, academic self-efficacy is the degree to which a student believes in their ability to cope with academic challenges, complete tasks, and achieve positive outcomes in their studies (Luckin et al., 2016; Pajares, 1996).

Academic self-efficacy affects many aspects of learning and academic success. Firstly, it has a direct effect on student motivation. Students with high self-efficacy tend to invest more effort in their studies, persist through complex tasks, and handle failures more productively. They view academic challenges as opportunities for growth rather than insurmountable obstacles. As a result, academic self-efficacy contributes to persistence in learning and to higher

achievements over time (Luckin et al., 2016; Schunk and Pajares, 2002).

In addition, academic self-efficacy also affects students’ emotions and attitudes toward learning. Students who believe that they are capable experience less test anxiety and less academic pressure because they are confident in their ability to handle their academic tasks. This sense of confidence allows them to approach learning with a positive attitude, which enhances their ability to concentrate, remember information, and apply it effectively. Furthermore, academic self-efficacy is linked to the ability to cope with failure – students with high self-efficacy tend to view failure as part of the learning process and use it as a learning experience for future self-improvement (Dweck, 2006; Howard and Mozejko, 2015).

Academic self-efficacy is also influenced and shaped by the learning environment and the social support that students receive. Teachers and parents play a crucial role in strengthening students’ sense of efficacy. Teachers who convey belief in their students’ abilities, provide their students with appropriate challenges, and offer constructive positive feedback may significantly enhance students’ sense of efficacy. Peer groups and the social environment at school also play an important role – positive support from friends may encourage students and strengthen their confidence in learning (Howard and Mozejko, 2015; Wentzel, 1998).

This notion of support extends into digital environments as well. Smith et al. (2015), who examined the use of communication technologies such as online forums and educational social networks, found that students who use these platforms feel a greater sense of belonging to their learning community and have higher academic self-efficacy. The ability to ask questions, receive quick answers, and share ideas with peers and teachers online empowers students’ self-confidence and belief in their ability to succeed academically.

Another study that contributed to a deeper understanding of academic self-efficacy is a study by Martin et al. (2003), which examines the effects of the learning environment and social support on student self-efficacy. The study found that supportive learning environments — including positive feedback and interactions with teachers and peers — significantly contribute to strengthening student self-efficacy. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance of creating a classroom climate that encourages cooperation and collaborative learning as part of the educational process. Students who are part of a supportive group are more likely to have higher self-efficacy and be willing to tackle challenging academic tasks.

Zimmerman and Cleary (2005) also examined the effects of academic self-efficacy on goal-setting and persistence in learning. They found that students with high self-efficacy tend to set higher academic goals for themselves and to persist in achieving them, even in the

face of difficulties and setbacks. High self-efficacy strengthens students' belief in their ability to achieve these goals, leading to greater persistence and higher academic achievements.

Finally, academic self-efficacy is a central component of students' academic success, influencing their motivation, emotions, and attitudes toward learning and playing a critical role in their ability to cope with academic challenges. A strong learning environment, which includes supportive teachers and positive peer groups, may empower students' self-efficacy and contribute to their academic success (Eccles and Wigfield, 2002; Pajares, 1996).

Factors that influence self-efficacy

Academic self-efficacy is shaped by various psychological, social, and environmental influences that collectively impact students' confidence in their ability to succeed in academic tasks. A crucial factor affecting self-efficacy is past experiences of success and failure. When students repeatedly succeed, especially in difficult circumstances, they build a stronger belief in their capacity to tackle future challenges. Conversely, repeated failures can weaken self-efficacy and foster feelings of helplessness and a diminished belief in their ability to improve and succeed (Zimmerman and Cleary, 2005).

External feedback is another significant factor that affects academic self-efficacy. Justified positive feedback from teachers, parents, and peers may strengthen a student's belief in their abilities. When students receive encouragement and support, they tend to view academic tasks as attainable challenges rather than insurmountable obstacles. Feedback must be specific and focused on students' efforts and learning process, not just on students' actual achievements, since recognition of students' efforts is more likely to encourage perseverance and strengthen student self-efficacy (Hattie and Timperley, 2007).

Social support is another factor that significantly influences academic self-efficacy. Social support may come from various sources, such as family, friends, teachers, and peers. A supportive and positive environment that provides help, encouragement, and understanding is more likely to assist students in developing self-confidence and persistence. Additionally, social relationships between classmates may also have an impact—when a student is part of a supportive collaborative group, they are more likely to feel confident in their abilities and to be willing to face academic challenges in an open, positive way (Bandura, 1997; Zimmerman and Cleary, 2005). The school climate and physical environment also influence academic self-efficacy. Schools that encourage a culture of support, cooperation, and appreciation create an environment in which students feel safe to experiment and learn from

mistakes. A learning environment that is accessible and tailored to diverse needs, including adapted educational materials and technological support, may strengthen self-efficacy in students with special needs and may increase their confidence in their ability to succeed academically (Eccles and Roeser, 2011; Zimmerman and Cleary, 2005).

Finally, personal psychological factors, such as self-image and belief in personal ability, significantly affect academic self-efficacy. Students with a positive self-image and strong belief in their abilities tend to approach academic tasks with greater confidence and persistence. These students can handle failures productively, see failures as part of the learning process, and use incidents of failure as opportunities for personal growth (Dweck, 2006; Zimmerman and Cleary, 2005). In other words, academic self-efficacy is the result of complex interactions between internal and external factors. It may be strengthened through experiences of success, positive feedback, social support, and a supportive learning environment. Many studies have been conducted in the field of academic self-efficacy, emphasizing its importance for academic success and the personal development of students. Bandura's research was among the pioneers in the field, highlighting the strong connection between personal self-efficacy and between academic persistence and performance. Bandura demonstrated that students with high self-efficacy are better able to handle academic challenges, show greater resilience in the face of failure, and achieve better results over time. These studies laid the foundation for understanding the importance of self-confidence and self-efficacy in the context of learning and academic success (Bandura, 1997).

Technology and academic self-efficacy

A wide range of digital technologies may influence academic self-efficacy; however, artificial intelligence tools represent a distinct category due to their ability to simulate human-like interaction, adapt in real time, and provide generative support. Unlike traditional platforms that offer static content or limited personalization, AI systems such as chatbots, adaptive tutors, and predictive feedback tools dynamically respond to students' needs, potentially reinforcing their belief in their academic capabilities. Use of technology in the classroom, such as traditional computers, tablet computers, and advanced educational software, offers a variety of tools that may strengthen student self-efficacy in various ways. Firstly, technology provides access to a wide range of information and educational resources, allowing students to learn at their own pace and independently address gaps in their knowledge. Free access to information may encourage students to take initiative in their learning and build self-efficacy through personal experiences of success (Luckin et al., 2016).

Furthermore, technology facilitates personalised instruction, addressing the unique needs of each student and significantly boosting students' academic self-efficacy. Online learning platforms, learning management systems (LMS), and advanced educational apps offer immediate personalised feedback, helping students identify their strengths and weaknesses and concentrate on areas requiring improvement. Immediate feedback enables students to monitor their progress in real-time, thereby strengthening their self-efficacy and fostering persistence and mastery. Consequently, students feel more confident in their ability to comprehend the material and advance in their learning (Howard and Mozejko, 2015; Seaman et al., 2020). Graham et al. found that when students receive instant interactive feedback through digital tools, they can see their progress immediately and correct their mistakes promptly, which enhances their sense of control and confidence (Graham et al., 2013).

Moreover, integrating technology into the classroom may improve students' motivation to learn. Educational games, virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR) may turn learning into a more engaging and enjoyable experience (Clark and Mayer, 2016; Dunleavy and Dede, 2014; Hew and Brush, 2007; Wu et al., 2013). When students feel that learning is a positive, intriguing experience, they tend to feel more confident in their ability to handle challenging academic tasks (Bandura, 1997). This high sense of self-efficacy motivates students to persist in their learning and achieve higher accomplishments (Johnson et al., 2016).

Furthermore, technology promotes collaboration and social learning through online platforms and collaborative tools. Students can work together on projects, share knowledge and ideas, and support each other in their learning (Molinillo et al., 2018; Voorn and Kommers, 2013). These social interactions enhance students' sense of belonging and security, and boost their self-efficacy by providing opportunities to see the impact of their work and receive support and feedback from their group (Chen et al., 2020; Johnson et al., 2016).

However, the impact of technology use on academic self-efficacy may also be negative if not appropriately managed. Excessive use of technology or over-dependence on digital devices may lead students to feel information overload or may lead to a decline in interpersonal interactions that are essential for developing social and emotional skills (Hauk and Matlen, 2018; Kirschner and De Bruyckere, 2017). Additionally, a lack of access to technology, as well as low digital skills, may deepen educational gaps and reduce self-efficacy among certain students (Chen et al., 2020; Livingstone, 2012). Technology offers significant tools that may enhance students' academic self-efficacy by providing access to information, personalized instruction, increased motivation, and options for collaboration (Chen et al.,

2020; Clark and Mayer, 2016). However, technology must be used mindfully and responsibly to avoid its negative effects and ensure that all students benefit from its advantages (Chen et al., 2020; Reich, 2020).

Aim and hypothesis of the study

The current study aims to investigate the extent to which students' self-reported use of AI tools correlates with their levels of academic self-efficacy, as measured by a modified general self-efficacy scale.

The current study investigates the following research question:

Does the use of AI tools correlate with academic self-efficacy among higher-education students?

Based on this question, the study explores the following hypothesis:

H1: There is a positive correlation between AI usage and academic self-efficacy among higher-education students in Israel.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Participants

The current study investigates the impact of using AI tools on academic self-efficacy among higher-education students. Correlational research design was employed for the study. The sample consisted of 102 participants (N = 102), who completed a survey approved by the ethics committee of **Ariel University** and in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, 2013 (protocol code AU-SOC-ND-20241229, December 29, 2024). The inclusion criteria for participation in the study were as follows: (1) participants had to be at least 18 years old, and (2) they had to be currently enrolled in undergraduate or graduate (second degree) programs in institutions of higher education. Participants from various academic institutions across Israel were recruited through voluntary responses to online calls. Those who did not complete the questionnaire in full were excluded from the final analysis. The data were collected between February 2023 and March 2024. The average age of the participants was 24.3 years (SD = 3.88), and their ages ranged from 22 to 35 years.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the participants according to various characteristics. Of the 102 participants, 37 were men (36.3%) and 65 were women (63.7%). The majority of participants were enrolled in undergraduate programs (N = 63), while the remainder were pursuing graduate (second degree) studies (N = 39).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of background variables.

Background variable	<i>N</i>	%	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Age	102	100	24.3	3.88
Gender				
Male	37	36.3		
Female	65	63.7		
Religiosity level				
Secular	21	20.6		
Orthodox	61	59.8		
Traditionalist	20	19.6		
Military/national service				
Yes	92	90.2		
No	10	9.8		
Level of education				
Undergraduate	63	61.8		
Graduate (2 nd degree)	39	38.2		

Research tools

A two-part socio-demographic questionnaire was used to examine control variables such as age, gender, military service, and academic background. The second part focused on AI usage and included two questions specifically designed for this study. These questions were approved by the ethics committee of Ariel University and aimed to assess how frequently students use AI and how proficient they feel with AI tools. The internal consistency of this short scale was acceptable ($\alpha = .678$). At the time of data collection, validated instruments for measuring AI usage in education were still limited, so the two questions served as initial indicators of general engagement and perceived usefulness. This approach corresponds with the exploratory nature of the study.

To assess academic self-efficacy, a well-established questionnaire was used. It is based on the general self-efficacy scale developed by Chen and Gully (1997) and revised by Chen, Gully and Eden (2001). The version used in this study was translated into Hebrew by Grant Plumin and has been used in previous research in this format. The questionnaire measures students' beliefs in their ability to set and achieve goals and to handle challenges in everyday academic life. It contains unidimensional items rated on a 3-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly disagree*, 3 =

strongly agree), with statements such as: "I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself," "When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will perform," and "In general, I think that I will be able to obtain outcomes that are important to me."

This self-efficacy scale has consistently demonstrated high reliability in international studies, with Cronbach's alpha ranging from .90 to .95. In the current study, the scale also showed strong internal consistency ($\alpha = .91$). The questionnaire has undergone rigorous validity testing and is recognized for its content and predictive validity. For this study, several minor wording adaptations were made to match the research context, with approval from the ethics committee.

In addition to the self-efficacy scale and AI usage questions, the questionnaire also included items assessing student satisfaction with the AI tools they use, the perceived effectiveness of these tools in the learning process, and their impact on students' motivation and academic performance. These items were developed specifically for this study to capture students' overall experience with AI in an educational setting. The combination of standardized and study-specific items allowed for a comprehensive quantitative analysis of the relationship between AI use and academic self-efficacy.

Table 2. Reliability of research tools (Cronbach's alpha).

Research tool	Cronbach's alpha	No. of Items
Self-efficacy questionnaire	0.905	8
AI questions (within socio-demographic questionnaire)	0.678	2

Procedure

The current study is correlational, examining the relationship between the research variables without examining how the variables affect each other. The data in the study were collected by distributing the research questionnaire via social-media platforms (WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram and more), after receiving approval from the ethics committee of Ariel University. Data collection took place between February 2023 and March 2024, during the early phase of public access to generative AI tools such as ChatGPT. At that time, most institutions had not yet developed clear pedagogical guidelines for educational AI use. Therefore, the findings reflect early-stage perceptions and engagement patterns, offering a valuable baseline for future longitudinal or comparative studies. At the beginning of the questionnaire, the participants were required to give their consent to completing the questionnaire by signing an informed consent form. The consent to participate confirms that the participants were aware of the research objectives, that there would be no compensation for completing the questionnaire, and that the participants took part in the study voluntarily.

The data were analyzed using the SPSS software,

including descriptive statistics for both the sample of study participants and the main research variables (AI and self-efficacy). The analysis examines the relationships between the main research variables using Pearson tests. Initially, 108 subjects ($N = 108$) participated, but six were excluded from the data analysis since they did not complete the entire questionnaire. Therefore, the findings of the study were analyzed based on the answers of the remaining 102 participants ($N = 102$).

RESULTS

The main findings of the current study regarding the relationship between the use of AI tools and student self-efficacy begin with an examination of the general tendencies in the sample. Overall, students demonstrated relatively high levels of academic self-efficacy, with low variability across responses. In contrast, the extent of AI tool usage showed greater individual variation, with scores covering the full range of the scale. These patterns suggest that while confidence in academic abilities is generally strong among participants, the integration of AI into academic routines remains inconsistent. The descriptive statistics for the key variables are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics.

Variable	Max.	Min.	SD	M	%	N
Self-efficacy	5	2	0.548	4.045	100	102
AI usage	5	1	0.981	2.951	100	102

Table 4 displays the distribution of participant responses to the two AI-related items: technological proficiency and frequency of AI tool usage. Over 60% of the students rated their technological proficiency as high or very high, indicating that the majority of participants felt confident using digital technologies. In terms of AI engagement,

more than 40% of respondents reported frequent use of AI tools, while approximately 17% reported low or no usage. These results reflect the varying degrees of AI adoption among students and form an important basis for analyzing its relationship with academic self-efficacy.

Table 4. Participants' self-reported technological proficiency and AI usage frequency.

Response category	Technological proficiency	%	AI usage frequency	N	%
Very low	2	2.0	Not at all	5	4.9
Low	8	7.8	Somewhat	12	11.8
Average	26	25.5	Average use	41	40.2
High	41	40.2	Much	31	30.4
Very high	25	24.5	Very much	13	12.7

Participants' academic self-efficacy levels were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, and their responses were categorized into five score ranges. Table 5 displays the

distribution of students across these ranges, from "very low" to "very high". The majority of participants reported high (3.50-4.49) or very high (4.50-5.00) self-efficacy

scores, while only a small number fell into the “low” or “moderate” categories. No students reported scores in the “very low” range.

Table 5. Distribution of participants by level of self-efficacy.

Self-efficacy score range	Description	N	%
1.00 – 1.99	Very low	0	0.0
2.00 – 2.99	Low	4	3.9
3.00 – 3.49	Moderate	17	16.7
3.50 – 4.49	High	57	55.9
4.50 – 5.00	Very high	24	23.5

Relationships between variables

To test the first hypothesis, which posits a correlation between AI usage and student self-efficacy, a Pearson

correlation test was conducted between the main research variables. Table 6 presents the correlations between the variables.

Table 6. Pearson correlations between the main research variables.

Variable	General AI usage	Technological proficiency	Extent of AI usage	Self-efficacy
General AI usage	1			
Technological proficiency	.830***	1		
Extent of AI usage	.920***	.545***	1	
Self-efficacy	.280**	.292**	.216**	1

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 6 shows that the first hypothesis, which assumed that a relationship exists between AI usage and self-efficacy, was confirmed ($r_p = .280$, $p < .01$). A weak but

statistically significant positive correlation was found, indicating that the more frequently students use AI tools, the higher their reported level of self-efficacy (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Academic self-efficacy across levels of AI tool usage among higher-education students.

Summary

To summarize this chapter, the findings of the current study indicate a statistically significant, albeit modest, correlation between AI usage and academic self-efficacy. Additionally, the distribution of responses reveals that a majority of students rated their academic self-efficacy as high or very high, underscoring the generally confident mindset of the sample.

DISCUSSION

The current study aimed to examine whether the use of AI tools is associated with academic self-efficacy among higher-education students, in response to the growing implementation of such technologies in learning environments (Huang and Qiao, 2024). The first research hypothesis predicted a positive correlation between the two variables. The findings confirmed this hypothesis, revealing a weak but statistically significant positive correlation between the use of AI tools and students' academic self-efficacy. The analysis showed that both students' technological proficiency and the frequency of AI use were positively associated with their self-efficacy scores. This conclusion aligns with previous research that has demonstrated similar associations between AI engagement and students' ability to manage academic tasks (Chen, 2017; Parsakia, 2023; Rodríguez-Ruiz et al., 2024; Yilmaz and Karaoglan Yilmaz, 2023).

A likely explanation for this relationship lies in the flexibility of AI tools to support both personalized teaching and self-paced learning. Such adaptability allows educators to tailor instruction and students to engage in ways that align with their individual learning preferences. As emphasized by Bendriem et al. (2018) and Harry and Sayudin (2023), this supports the development of academic autonomy and self-directed learning – critical elements of self-efficacy.

While the correlation identified in this study is modest and does not establish a causal relationship, it nevertheless emphasizes the potential of AI tools to enhance students' academic confidence and autonomy. Previous research has similarly suggested that AI-integrated educational environments may foster key psychological conditions for self-efficacy by reducing academic stress, increasing motivation, and offering instant, personalized feedback (Luckin et al., 2016; Holmes et al., 2019).

While the findings indicate a positive association between AI usage and academic self-efficacy, it is important to consider potential moderating factors. Prior research has identified skeptical or critical attitudes toward the use of AI in educational settings among both students and faculty (Davidovitch and Wadmany, 2021; Keleş and Aydın, 2021). These attitudes often stem from concerns

about academic integrity, ethical implications, or apprehension about AI replacing human educators (Chan, 2023). Such perceptions may influence how effectively students engage with AI tools and thus impact the development of self-efficacy.

To build on these findings, further research should identify the specific conditions that enhance students' meaningful engagement with AI tools in academic contexts. In particular, future studies may explore mediating and moderating variables such as prior exposure to digital technologies, levels of digital self-efficacy, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, and the pedagogical approaches used to introduce AI. Understanding these factors can help optimize the integration of AI in higher education and support the development of students' academic competencies and confidence.

Limitations of the study

Although the current study emphasizes the importance of integrating AI into education, it has some limitations. Firstly, the sample that was used herein is not representative of the greater population, comprising only about 102 participants, so the findings cannot be generalized to the entire population. Additionally, the section of the research questionnaire that examines the participants' knowledge and use of AI tools was developed independently and contains only two items. Moreover, although the study was conducted at an early stage of AI integration in education, between February 2023 and March 2024, when formal guidelines and societal norms were still emerging, it is still possible that some participants underreported their AI use due to perceived academic expectations. Additionally, as ethical norms around the use of AI in academic settings were still taking shape at the time of data collection, some students may have exercised caution in disclosing the extent of their AI usage. While not necessarily indicative of deliberate underreporting, this cautiousness could reflect early-stage uncertainties about acceptable academic practices, which future studies may address more systematically. However, given the novelty and limited functionality of AI tools at the time, such bias is likely to have been minimal. Therefore, despite the high reliability of these two questions, they may not suffice to accurately measure participants' level of knowledge or use of AI-based tools. Finally, the significant difference in participation rates between students and non-students makes it difficult to determine whether the findings are reliable.

Future studies

Building on the present findings, future research may

explore several promising directions. One potential area involves examining how academic self-efficacy and the use of AI tools vary across different academic disciplines. Investigating whether students in fields such as the humanities, sciences, or engineering engage differently with AI-based technologies may offer valuable insights into the contextual factors that shape technological adoption and its effects on learning.

Another relevant line of inquiry involves gender. Future studies could analyse whether there are meaningful differences in AI usage patterns or self-efficacy levels between male and female students, or across other gender identities. Such research could help ensure equitable access to the benefits of AI integration in education.

Longitudinal research may also provide a deeper understanding of how sustained AI usage influences academic self-efficacy over time. Observing students across multiple semesters or academic years could reveal whether the benefits of AI tools persist, diminish, or evolve with continued use.

Ultimately, future research may integrate both quantitative and qualitative methods, providing a more comprehensive understanding of students' personal experiences, challenges, and attitudes toward AI in educational settings. This could lead to the development of more tailored and effective pedagogical approaches that utilize artificial intelligence.

Another important direction for future research involves the potential influence of social desirability bias on self-reported AI usage, particularly among university students. Given the increasing concern over academic dishonesty and plagiarism, students may underreport their use of AI tools out of fear of being perceived as unethical. Future studies could explore this possibility using indirect questioning techniques, anonymity safeguards, or qualitative interviews to better understand the social and psychological factors influencing disclosure.

Future research conducted at later stages of AI adoption may encounter stronger effects of social desirability bias, particularly as institutional policies become stricter. Comparative studies across different time points would be valuable in tracking changes in perception, use, and openness about AI technologies in education.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study demonstrates a significant, albeit modest, positive correlation between the use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools and academic self-efficacy among higher-education students. These findings support the first hypothesis and contribute to the growing body of research suggesting that digital technologies, and AI in particular, may support student confidence and academic self-management.

Although no significant differences were found in AI usage between students and non-students, the study confirms that higher-education students report significantly higher self-efficacy. This finding aligns with the expectations of academic environments, where students are required to develop autonomy, persistence, and motivation—factors directly associated with self-efficacy. The lack of difference in AI usage between groups, however, highlights the widespread diffusion of AI tools beyond formal education settings and underscores the need for institutions to better support students in the purposeful and ethical use of AI for learning.

Notably, the study confirms that even among students who already possess relatively high levels of self-efficacy, the integration of AI tools is associated with slightly higher reported levels of self-efficacy, particularly in demanding academic contexts. This suggests that AI technologies should be considered not merely as optional add-ons but as strategic tools within higher education systems aimed at strengthening academic outcomes, reducing student burnout, and fostering motivation and resilience. However, as this is a correlational study, no causal conclusions can be drawn.

These findings have clear implications for curriculum developers, educational policymakers, and technology designers. Institutions of higher learning should consider systematically incorporating AI-based learning environments, with a focus on personalisation, accessibility, and user training. Furthermore, teacher preparation programs should include components on AI literacy to ensure that future educators are equipped to guide students in the meaningful and responsible use of such technologies.

While the study is limited by its relatively small sample size and the unbalanced representation of student and non-student groups, the results provide a compelling starting point for further exploration. Future studies should replicate these findings with larger and more diverse samples, incorporate qualitative data to explore the nuances of student experiences, and investigate long-term impacts of sustained AI use on academic self-efficacy and performance.

In conclusion, this research reinforces the educational potential of artificial intelligence and positions self-efficacy as a key psychological mechanism through which AI can contribute to student success.

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